

Assessment of Farmers' and Office Bearers' Satisfaction with Custom Hiring Centres in Haryana

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The study was conducted in 2024 to assess the satisfaction level of farmers and office bearers regarding Custom Hiring Centres in Haryana. A total of 200 respondents (120 farmers & 80 office bearers) from four purposively selected districts, namely Kaithal, Jind, Fatehabad and Sirsa, were chosen to collect data. Simple random sampling was employed in the selection of blocks, custom hiring centres and respondents. The satisfaction level is analyzed using the Total Weighted Score (TWS) and Weighted Mean Score (WMS), while the relationship between variables is examined using correlation and multiple regression analyses. The findings reveal that farmers express the highest satisfaction with the convenience of hiring machinery without ownership (WMS = 2.67) and with the machinery rental procedure (WMS = 2.66). However, lower satisfaction is observed with respect to technical guidance and maintenance services. Among office bearers, the overall financial stability of the business (WMS = 1.62) ranks highest, whereas government financial support (WMS = 0.85) ranks lowest. Extension contacts, mass media exposure, participation in extension activities, economic motivation, farm power availability, and scientific orientation are significantly positively related to satisfaction levels. The regression model explains 59.7% of the variation among farmers and 62.3% among office bearers. The study highlights the importance of strengthening technical support, training, and institutional assistance to enhance the effectiveness and sustainability of Custom Hiring Centres.

Keywords: Custom hiring centres, satisfaction level, utilization, farm mechanization, farmers

India is a predominantly agricultural country and 47 per cent of the population depends on it for their livelihood (PIB, 2023). The average operational land holding is estimated at 1.16 hectares and nearly 86.08 per cent of the land holdings are operated by marginal and small farmers owning less than 1 and 1-2 hectares, respectively (MoA & FW, 2021). Farm mechanization, also known as agricultural mechanization (AM), is a broad field with various aspects (Emami et al., 2018) that generally refers to the use of tools, implements, and other machinery to enhance agricultural productivity (Houmy et al., 2013). Mechanization encompasses all levels of farming and processing technologies, from simple, basic hand tools to more sophisticated, motorized equipment (FAO, 2024). Any stage of

agricultural production can benefit from mechanization (Emami et al., 2018). AM's primary goal is resource efficiency, and it offers farmers a number of social and financial advantages (G.C. et al., 2019). Farm mechanization is thought to have decreased the cost of human labor by 20%, animal labor by 60%, and seeds and fertilizers by 15%. In wheat crops, automation led to a 10% increase in output, a 25% decrease in seed costs, a 30% decrease in irrigation water costs, and time savings for farm managers (Prasad et al., 2014).

The availability of land, labor, and capital is crucial to agriculture, with labor being one of the most crucial inputs in farm operations. Lack of agricultural labour is one of the main problems faced by Indian farmers in rural areas (Kadaraiah et al., 2022). The increase in labour costs has made it harder for farmers to get fair prices for their produce. By reducing input costs, reducing drudgery, and enabling the timely completion of farm operations, agricultural mechanization plays a vital role in increasing agricultural output. Mechanization remains out of reach for many marginal and small farmers nationwide, although it is typically found among farmers with large operating holdings (Shyam et al., 2023). One of the main obstacles to agricultural production has been identified as the lack of farm machinery, particularly for marginal and small farmers (Ghanghas et al., 2024). Before the Sub-Mission on Agricultural Mechanization (SMAM) program was implemented, the average Farm Power Availability in India was 1.84 kW/ha. Farm power of 2.5 kW/ha by 2022 and 4.00 kW/ha by 2030 is considered essential to achieving the necessary production intensity and cropping average (Final Report on M & E SMAM, 2018). One of the main obstacles to the growth of agriculture and the rise in its production and productivity is the lack of farm equipment and power, particularly for farmers with modest land holdings. The problem of low productivity can be addressed by expanding access to high-end farm

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equipment for small and marginal farmers. The majority of farmers in the nation, however, are unable to purchase costly farm equipment; as a result, they may turn to custom hiring centres for machinery on a rental basis (Kisku & Bisht, 2022).

Custom Hiring Centres (CHCs) are units that comprise farm machinery, implements, and equipment for custom hiring by farmers (Rao et al., 2023). The government of Haryana has established 6,755 custom hiring service centres from 2018-19 to 2022-23 under the scheme entitled "Promotion of Agricultural Mechanization for In-Situ Management of Crop Residue in Punjab, Haryana, Uttar Pradesh and NCT of Delhi". The burning of paddy straw here poses a significant environmental challenge. The special thing is that these CHCs are playing a pivotal role in managing Parali (Government of Haryana, 2021). Due to the high cost of farm machinery and the fragmented nature of agricultural land held predominantly by small and marginal farmers, mechanization becomes challenging. By utilizing the services of custom hiring centres, small and marginal farmers can access a range of agricultural implements to increase crop production and productivity, without investing in their purchase. The development of custom hiring mechanisms not only improves access to machinery for small and marginal farmers but also provides better services to farmers.

Custom Hiring Centres, therefore, serve as an important institutional mechanism to provide affordable mechanization services to farmers while also generating income opportunities for entrepreneurs and farmer organizations managing these centres. The effectiveness and sustainability of Custom Hiring Centres largely depend on the satisfaction and participation of both farmers who use the services and office bearers who manage operations (Das & Patil, 2024). Although several studies have examined the utilization and constraints of Custom Hiring Centres across different parts of India, little research has examined the satisfaction levels of both farmers and office bearers simultaneously, particularly in Haryana. Therefore, the present study was undertaken to assess the satisfaction level of farmers and office bearers regarding Custom Hiring Centres and to analyse the factors influencing their satisfaction.

Method

The present study was conducted in four districts of Haryana, viz, Sirsa, Fatehabad, Kaithal and Jind. The districts were selected purposively based on the highest number of Custom Hiring Centres. Furthermore, two blocks were randomly selected from each district. From each of the eight blocks, five custom hiring centres, and from each CHC, two office bearers and three beneficiary farmers were selected as respondents for the study, who availed the services of CHCs and the office bearers associated with these centres, using simple random sampling for personal interviews. Thus, a total of 200 respondents (80 CHC office bearers & 120 beneficiary farmers) were selected for the study. An ex-post facto research design was used because the variables had already occurred and were beyond the researcher's control. The data were collected using a structured, pre-tested interview schedule. The schedule included statements on various aspects of Custom Hiring Centres, such as availability of farm machinery, quality of machinery, operational efficiency, technical guidance, and service support. The respondents were personally interviewed to obtain reliable information. The satisfaction level of farmers and office bearers towards CHCs was measured using a three-point continuum with scores of 3, 2, and 1 for

satisfied, somewhat satisfied, and dissatisfied, respectively. The collected data were coded, tabulated and analyzed using appropriate statistical tools. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to describe the satisfaction level of respondents. Weighted Mean Score and ranking techniques were applied to analyze different aspects of satisfaction. Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to examine the relationship between socio-personal characteristics of respondents and their satisfaction level. Multiple regression analysis was employed to determine the influence of independent variables on farmers' and office bearers' satisfaction levels regarding Custom Hiring Centres.

Results

The data in Figures 1 and 2 reveal that a considerable proportion of respondents from both groups expressed moderate satisfaction. Nearly half of farmers (46.00%) reported being somewhat satisfied with the services provided by CHCs, followed by fully satisfied (31.00%) reported being fully satisfied. However, a notable proportion of farmers (23.00%) were dissatisfied with the services. A similar pattern was observed for office bearers: somewhat satisfied (48.00%), followed by fully satisfied (35.00%) and dissatisfied (17.00%).

The data presented in Table 1 revealed farmers' levels of satisfaction with different aspects of CHCs. Among the various aspects, the convenience of hiring machinery without the burden of ownership was ranked first (WMS = 2.67). This indicated that farmers highly appreciated the opportunity to access farm machinery without investing in costly equipment. The procedure followed by the society when providing machines on rent was ranked second (WMS = 2.66), and dealing with staff was ranked third (WMS = 2.58), suggesting that staff behaviour and cooperation were perceived positively by the respondents. The availability of different types of machinery that met the requirements of diverse farming practices was ranked fourth (WMS = 2.15). Similarly, the availability of up-to-date equipment aligned with modern farming needs was ranked fifth (WMS = 2.14). The condition and quality of machinery provided by CHCs received the sixth rank (WMS = 2.10), followed by the timely availability of farm machinery which was ranked seventh (WMS = 2.09). Rental rates for farm machinery ranked eighth, with a WMS of 1.96. The technical guidance provided by office bearers regarding the use of machinery was ranked last (WMS = 1.62), suggesting that farmers perceived this aspect as relatively weak.

Figure 1

Overall Satisfaction Level of Farmers towards CHCs (n=120)

Figure 2

Overall Satisfaction Level of Office Bearers towards CHCs (n=80)

Table 2 illustrates the satisfaction level of office bearers regarding various operational aspects of Custom Hiring Centres. The results indicated that the overall financial stability of their business was ranked first with the highest weighted mean score (WMS = 1.62). This suggested that office bearers perceived their enterprises to be relatively stable financially. The quality and condition of the machinery in their fleet were ranked second (WMS = 1.49), followed by the equipment's ability to meet customer needs, which ranked third (WMS = 1.46). Maintenance and repair costs were ranked ninth (WMS = 1.02), indicating concerns among office bearers about the associated expenses. The availability of technical training for handling and maintaining machinery was ranked tenth (WMS = 0.92). Government financial support received the lowest rank (WMS = 0.85), indicating dissatisfaction among office bearers regarding institutional support.

Table 1

Satisfaction Level of Farmers towards Custom Hiring Centres (n=120)

S. No.	Aspect of CHCs	TWS	WMS	Rank
1	Timely availability of farm machinery at CHCs	251	2.09	VII
2	Equipment provided by CHCs is up-to-date and in line with modern farming needs	257	2.14	V
3	Rental rates of farm machinery at CHCs	236	1.96	VIII
4	The convenience of hiring machinery without the hassle of ownership	321	2.67	I
5	Condition and quality of the machinery provided by CHC	253	2.10	VI
6	Availability of additional services, such as maintenance and repair support	198	1.65	IX
7	Types of machinery available at CHC adequately meet the demands of different farming practices	259	2.15	IV
8	Dealing with staff	310	2.58	III
9	Procedure followed by the society while renting the machines	320	2.66	II
10	Technical guidance provided by the office bearer of CHC regarding the use of machineries	195	1.62	X

Note. TWS = Total weighted score, WMS = Weighted mean score

Table 2

Satisfaction Level of Farmers towards Custom Hiring Centres (n=120)

S. No.	Aspect of CHCs	TWS	WMS	Rank
1.	The ability of my staff to operate and maintain the equipment	167	1.39	VI
2.	The overall financial stability of my business	195	1.62	I
3.	Quality and condition of the machinery in my fleet	179	1.49	II
4.	Maintenance and repair costs for equipment are reasonable	123	1.02	IX
5.	The downtime due to equipment repairs is minimal and manageable	172	1.43	V
6.	Spare parts for my machinery are easily accessible and affordable	156	1.30	VII
7.	Equipment in my fleet fulfills the needs of my customers	176	1.46	III
8.	Provide timely and reliable service to farmers during peak seasons	175	1.45	IV
9.	The government provides adequate financial support	103	0.85	XI
10.	The availability of technical training to handle and maintain agricultural machinery	111	0.92	X
11.	The insurance coverage available for my equipment	138	1.15	VIII

Note. TWS = Total weighted score, WMS = Weighted mean score)

The results of the correlation and regression analyses presented in Table 3 reveal that $R^2 = 0.597$, indicating that about 59.7 per cent of the variation in satisfaction level is explained by the selected independent variables. Variables such as education, cropping pattern, source of irrigation, farm power implements, participation in extension activities, extension contact, mass media exposure, economic motivation, and scientific orientation showed significant positive relationships with farmers' satisfaction levels. Among these

variables, farm power implements exhibited the strongest influence on satisfaction level ($t = 3.34$), followed by mass media exposure, extension contact, and economic motivation. On the other hand, variables such as age, landholding, annual income, and farming experience showed no significant relationships with farmers' satisfaction levels. The adjusted coefficient of determination (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.551$) further indicated that the regression model had a good explanatory power.

Table 3

Relationship of the Socio-personal Profile of Farmers with their Satisfaction Level about CHCs (n=120)

S. No.	Independent variables	Correlation Coefficient	B-Value	Standard error	t
1	Age	0.023 ^{NS}	0.015	0.041	0.37 ^{NS}
2	Education	0.233*	0.184	0.073	2.52*
3	Land holding	0.072 ^{NS}	0.051	0.046	1.11 ^{NS}
4	Cropping Pattern	0.198*	0.162	0.068	2.38*
5	Source of Irrigation	0.214*	0.171	0.071	2.41*
6	Annual Income	0.041 ^{NS}	0.028	0.044	0.64 ^{NS}
7	Farm power implements	0.288**	0.231	0.069	3.34**
8	Farming experience	0.031 ^{NS}	0.020	0.042	0.48 ^{NS}
9	Participation in extension activity	0.245**	0.198	0.066	3.00**
10	Extension contact	0.267**	0.213	0.067	3.18**
11	Mass media exposure	0.277**	0.221	0.068	3.25**
12	Economic motivation	0.261**	0.208	0.067	3.10**
13	Scientific orientation	0.249**	0.201	0.066	3.05**
	R ²			0.597	
	Adjusted R ²			0.551	
	Constant			4.87	

Note: NS= non-significant, **=Significant at 0.01 level of significance, *= Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 4

Relationship of the Socio-personal Profile of Office Bearers with their Satisfaction Level about CHCs (n= 80)

S. No.	Independent variables	Correlation Coefficient	B-Value	Standard error	t
1	Age	0.041 ^{NS}	0.028	0.043	0.65 ^{NS}
2	Education	0.221*	0.176	0.071	2.47*
3	Land holding	0.271**	0.214	0.069	3.10**
4	Cropping Pattern	0.189*	0.151	0.067	2.25*
5	Source of Irrigation	0.233*	0.186	0.072	2.58*
6	Annual Income	0.264**	0.209	0.068	3.07**
7	Farm power implements	0.274**	0.218	0.069	3.16**
8	Farming experience	0.247*	0.197	0.071	2.77*
9	Participation in extension activity	0.261**	0.208	0.067	3.10**
10	Extension contact	0.281**	0.224	0.068	3.29**
11	Mass media exposure	0.269**	0.215	0.067	3.21**
12	Economic motivation	0.239**	0.191	0.066	2.89**
13	Scientific orientation	0.241**	0.194	0.066	2.94**
	R ²			0.623	
	Adjusted R ²			0.571	
	Constant			3.98	

Note. NS= non-significant, **=Significant at 0.01 level of significance, *= Significant at 0.05 level of significance)

The data in Table 4 present the relationship between the socio-personal characteristics of office bearers and their satisfaction levels regarding CHCs. The regression model explained 62.3 per cent of the variation in satisfaction level ($R^2 = 0.623$), while the adjusted R^2 value of 0.571 indicated a good model fit. The results revealed that several variables, such as education, land holding, cropping pattern, source of irrigation, annual income, farm power implements,

farming experience, participation in extension activities, extension contact, mass media exposure, economic motivation, and scientific orientation, showed significant positive relationships with satisfaction level. Among these variables, extension contact showed the highest influence on satisfaction level ($t = 3.29$), followed by mass media exposure, farm power implements and participation in extension activities.

However, age showed a non-significant relationship with the satisfaction level of office bearers. Overall, the findings suggested that access to information, technological orientation and farm resources played a significant role in determining the satisfaction level of office bearers regarding the functioning of Custom Hiring Centres.

Discussion

The findings indicate that farmers show a relatively higher level of satisfaction with the convenience of hiring machinery without the burden of ownership. The procedure followed by the society while providing machinery on rent was satisfactory, and farmers were also satisfied with the staff's dealings. This suggests that Custom Hiring Centres (CHCs) play a significant role in improving access to farm mechanization, especially for farmers who cannot afford to purchase costly agricultural machinery. The availability of machinery on a rental basis reduces capital investment and enables small and marginal farmers to adopt improved farm technologies. These findings are consistent with the observations of Dash et al. (2019) and Villalba et al. (2024) who report that CHCs significantly enhance the accessibility of farm machinery among resource-poor farmers. Whereas efficient management procedures encourage farmers to utilize CHCs more frequently. Similar findings are reported by Chandrashekar (2016) and Shobha et al. (2018) who note that institutional arrangements and simplified rental procedures increase farmer participation in mechanization services. Good staff behavior often improves trust and encourages repeated use of institutional services. This observation aligns with Shyam et al. (2023) findings, who emphasize that service quality and staff responsiveness play an important role in farmer satisfaction. However, the results reveal relatively lower satisfaction regarding technical guidance. Similar concerns are highlighted by Kisku and Singh (2022) who report that inadequate technical support remains a major constraint on CHCs' effective functioning.

Office bearers are mostly satisfied with their business's overall financial stability. This implies that CHCs provide a viable income-generating opportunity for operators and organizations managing the centres. This finding is supported by Murugesan (2019) who highlights that CHCs can operate as profitable rural enterprises when properly managed. Nevertheless, the lowest levels of satisfaction are observed regarding government financial support. This suggests that office bearers perceive a lack of institutional support for effectively managing CHCs. These results are consistent with Nishanthi (2023) findings, which report that limited government support often constrains the performance of Custom Hiring Centres. Moreover, findings suggest that farmers who are more exposed to agricultural information and extension services tend to have greater awareness and better utilization of CHC services. This observation supports the findings of Shyam et al. (2023) and Nandhini and Rohini (2022) who emphasize that extension communication significantly influences the adoption of agricultural innovations.

The significant influence of annual income and farm power implements indicates that economically stronger office bearers with better access to mechanization resources tend to experience higher satisfaction levels. Financial capacity allows them to maintain machinery properly and provide better services to farmers.

Conclusion

The study concludes that farmers report moderate to high

satisfaction with CHC services. Among the various aspects, farmers express the highest satisfaction with the convenience of hiring machinery without the burden of ownership and with the procedures involved in renting machinery. These aspects highlight the important role of CHCs in improving access to farm mechanization, particularly for small and marginal farmers who cannot afford expensive agricultural machinery. However, farmers report comparatively lower satisfaction with technical guidance, maintenance services, and rental charges, indicating a need to strengthen support services at the centres. This suggests that while CHCs successfully address the issue of machinery availability, additional technical and advisory services are necessary to maximize their effectiveness. The findings regarding office bearers indicate that they are relatively satisfied with the business's financial stability and the quality of machinery. Nevertheless, they express lower satisfaction regarding government financial support, training opportunities, and maintenance costs, suggesting that institutional support mechanisms need to be strengthened. The correlation and regression analysis further reveal that variables such as extension contact, participation in extension activities, mass media exposure, economic motivation, farm power availability, and scientific orientation significantly influence the satisfaction level of both farmers and office bearers. These findings indicate that access to information and extension services plays a crucial role in enhancing awareness and effective utilization of CHCs. Policymakers should strengthen technical training, improve financial assistance, and enhance extension support to improve the operational efficiency of Custom Hiring Centres.

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